

PRAGMALINGUISTIC FEATURES OF THE POSITIVE SHIFT OF NEGATIVELY EVALUATED WORDS

Umarova Zumradxon Avazxon qizi

Kokand State University, Uzbekistan

Doctorate student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17414156>

Annotation

This article analyzes the process of the positive shift of negatively evaluated words from a pragmalinguistic perspective. Drawing upon the theoretical views of scholars such as S. Ullmann, N. Arutyunova, and Y. Volf, the study demonstrates the dependence of evaluative change on social, cultural, and contextual factors. It highlights the role of communicative intention, speech situation, intonation, and social values in the process of evaluative amelioration. The author concludes that the positive shift of negative evaluation is not a purely linguistic but a pragmalinguistic phenomenon.

Key words: evaluation, positive shift, negative evaluation, pragmalinguistics, communicative intention, connotation, context, linguistic unit.

It is known that in the linguistic discourse of the 1930s, scholars began to discuss the method of direct and indirect evaluation of a speech object through lexical-semantic units. Since that period, scientific and theoretical works have emphasised that the acts of direct and indirect evaluation are manifested through general evaluative and specific evaluative lexicon. The division of evaluative acts into direct and indirect assessments later led to the distinction between general and specific evaluative vocabulary. Usually, specific evaluative vocabulary and general evaluative vocabulary constitute two main types of axiological (value-related) meanings existing within a language system. While general evaluative meanings express a value-based result, specific evaluative meanings convey an assessment of a certain aspect of an object from a particular point of view¹.

In the above-mentioned scientific and theoretical interpretations, the act of evaluation is understood as a semantic phenomenon expressing a positive or negative attitude toward a speech object based on a certain criterion. In a general evaluative act, a value-based attitude is expressed toward the entire essence of the speech object—one that does not contradict societal norms. For instance, in such word combinations as “*good person*” or “*successful experiment*,” the positive evaluation of the speech object aligns with socially accepted criteria. In a specific evaluative act, however, only a certain property or function of the speech object

¹ Емельянова Ю.И. Способы выражения оценки в научном лингвистическом дискурсе (на примере публикаций 30-х гг. XX в.) // Вестник ЧГУП, 2010. – №2. – С. 204

is assessed. For example, in “a wonderful car” or “a gentle man,” the positive assessment concerns not the general essence but a particular aspect of the object. Thus, in general evaluation, the characteristic elevated to the level of value is indicated, whereas in specific evaluation, a certain aspect of the object receives positive assessment².

In linguistics, the phenomenon of the positive shift of negative evaluation was studied by S. Ullmann under the term “amelioration.” He defined it as “the process by which a word acquires a more favourable meaning or connotation”³. According to Ullmann, words can alter their evaluative quality in a positive direction. This phenomenon is associated with social, cultural, and psychological factors. For example, in English, the word “nice” originally had the negative meaning of “foolish, ignorant” but later acquired the positive meaning “pleasant, good, gentle.” The scholar noted that the causes of amelioration are varied: (1) social prestige – professions, titles, and ranks generally receive higher evaluations; (2) euphemisation – replacing unpleasant notions with milder expressions; and (3) subjective factors – fashion, emotional associations, literary and religious influence (“The causes of amelioration are various: social prestige, the tendency of euphemism, and subjective associations often play a decisive role.”).

For some reason, S. Ullmann uses the terms *amelioration of meaning* and *amelioration of evaluation* interchangeably. In our view, it would be more accurate to employ the term *amelioration of evaluation*, since it is not the meaning itself but rather the evaluation that shifts from negative to positive or vice versa. If we accept the idea that meaning itself can be positive or negative, it becomes necessary to distinguish between positive and negative meaning and positive and negative evaluation. However, in our opinion, such a distinction is hardly possible. Therefore, as Academician Azim Hojiyev⁴ and Professor Miraziz Mirtojdiyev⁵ have stated, evaluation or connotation is an additional aspect within the semantics of a word—a supplementary feature. Evaluation or connotativity constitutes an emotional colouring that joins the meaning of the word and expresses the addresser’s subjective attitude.

² Арутюнова Н.Д. Типы языковых значений. Оценка. Событие. Факт. – М.: Наука, 1988. – С. 75.

³ Ullmann S. Semantics: an introduction to the science of meaning. – Oxford: Basil Blackwell, 1964. – P. 220

⁴ Ҳожиёв А. тилшунослик терминларининг изоҳли луғати. - Тошкент: “Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси” давлат илмий нашриёти, 2002. – Б. 51-52.

⁵ Миртожйев М. Ўзбек тили семасиологияси. - Тошкент: “Университет” нашриёти, 2010. – Б. 281-283.

The inseparability of subjective evaluation from the meaning of a linguistic unit and the correctness of the view that evaluation is added to meaning as a supplementary feature can be substantiated further. When a negatively evaluated word undergoes positive re-evaluation, it is introduced into a positively charged discourse. In this process, the meaning of the word first changes; this semantic change naturally entails a modification of the word's evaluation.

One of the distinctions between our analysis and S. Ullmann's approach lies in the nature of the examples he provided. The cases of evaluative change he cites concern words that were neutral or negatively evaluated at one stage of language development but later acquired a positive evaluation in a subsequent period. Such cases indeed represent amelioration. However, in our research, we analyse the process of evaluative amelioration occurring within the same linguistic period, determined by the communicative situation. In other respects, our conclusions are largely aligned with those of the English linguist. For instance, in English, the adjective "*deafening*" originally carries a negative connotation. Yet, due to communicative purpose, in the expression "*a deafening silence*," it conveys a positive or emphatic meaning. Similarly, "*awfully*" is a word of originally negative evaluation; however, speakers use it positively in expressions such as "*awfully nice*." These examples of amelioration are characteristic of modern English usage.

The positive shift of negative evaluation in language is not a rare phenomenon⁶. Pragmalinguistic studies have demonstrated that such evaluative transformations exist in all languages. Indeed, evaluation is one of the crucial aspects of human intellectual activity. It is grounded in the system of human values and the relationship between categories such as truth and falsehood, good and evil. Through evaluation, a person perceives the surrounding world, and virtually all objects may become subjects of evaluation. Hence, interest in studying evaluation as a universal category has never waned. N. D. Arutyunova, in her work "Language and the World of Man," emphasises that "the role of evaluation in human life is immense. Evaluation determines decision-making and the choice of life paths."

E. M. Volf, in one of her studies, points out that every language possesses entire lexical layers designed to express subjective evaluation and provides a detailed analysis of them. Primarily, these are adjectives and adverbs, which enable the expression of various nuances of evaluative semantics. In addition, subjective evaluation can also be expressed by units smaller than the word (such

⁶ Данилова Р.Р. Категория оценки как способ выражения антропоцентризма в лингвистике // Вестник ТГГПУ, 2011. – № 23. + С. 137–139;

as affixes, suffixes, and other morphological forms). Thus, evaluativity can characterise both individual words and entire sentences⁷.

We also agree with Y. Volf's perspective. Indeed, the fact that languages possess such capacity creates opportunities for individuals to express their subjective attitudes in diverse ways. As Volf observed, linguistic units at different levels can undergo evaluative change. However, the substitution of one evaluation for another—particularly at the level of words—is especially distinctive. According to our findings, linguistic units other than words, such as affixes or sentences, rarely exhibit this phenomenon of transforming a negative evaluation into a positive one.

The process of amelioration of negatively evaluated words in a language can be represented by words belonging to different grammatical categories. Nevertheless, linguists often highlight the productivity of adjectives in this regard. Still, in our view, it would be accurate to mention the productivity of adverbs and nouns as well. In Uzbek literary language, coarse words such as *qistaloq*, *zang'ar*, *bachchag'ar*, and *battol* acquire positive connotations when used in positively charged discourses, distancing themselves from their original coarse meanings.

These words possess positive evaluations only within the specific discourse in which they appear and may not carry such connotations in other contexts. The appropriate communicative situation thus serves as the main factor contributing to the positive evaluation of these coarse, negatively connoted words. Therefore, it would be correct to consider such evaluations as pragmatic evaluations. In Uzbek language, for example: "*Shu-u,*" – *deydi amaki salmoqlanib,* – "*anchadan beri Abdurayim qattiqning cho'pon uliga uch-to'rt so'mdan berib turaman, baraka topsin, bolapaqir bizding siyirlardi bir boshqacha to'ydirib, sag'rinini yaltiratib qaytadi-ey. Bilmadim, ukag'ar, yem-pem beradima?.. otasiga rahmat, ammo-lekigin.*" (Abduqayum Yo'ldosh, Sahrodagi muhabbat)

In the above discourse, the coarse, negatively evaluated word **ukag'ar** is used in a complimentary sense, thereby acquiring a positive evaluation. The positive reinterpretation of this word arises not only from the speaker's communicative intention but also from the positively charged discourse, including expressions such as *baraka topsin* ("may he be blessed") and *otasiga rahmat* ("thanks to his father").

Positive evaluative shifts are often encountered in words and expressions. For instance, the word "*demon*" may possess two different evaluations. The

⁷ Степанова А.С. Языковые средства выражения категории оценки в публицистических текстах В.Н. Гиппиус (1920-1927 гг.). – Томск, 2016. – С. 12-13.

phrase “*devil spirit*” carries the primary meaning of “*evil spirit*” and is traditionally perceived negatively within Western linguistic culture. This standard semantics is associated with a negative evaluation, and recipients generally interpret it as such. However, in certain communicative situations, the word “*devil*” may also be understood positively. In such contexts, it is used to describe a person who is highly talented or exceptionally inventive. In these cases, the word “*devil*” acquires an occasional positive evaluation (occasional amelioration) and somewhat departs from its conventional semantics. Creative speakers employ such uses to generate unique expressive meanings.

The process of positive shift in negative evaluation resembles that of positive shift in neutral evaluation, in that both involve the transformation of one evaluative meaning into another within a single linguistic unit. However, in the amelioration of neutral evaluation, there is no contradiction between the unit’s habitual (usual) evaluation and its occasional one. In contrast, the positive shift of negative evaluation creates a conflict between the word’s usual (lexical) and occasional (contextual) evaluations. This process also gives rise to enantiosemy, a lexical phenomenon based on the opposition of two meanings within a single word.

In linguistic scholarship, there exist two opposing perspectives on this issue: some linguists regard this as a case of enantiosemy, while others argue that it should not be classified as such. Proponents of both positions can be found across different linguistic traditions — English, Russian, and Uzbek among them. For instance, the Russian specialist in English, L. V. Minayeva, considers the positive shift of negative evaluation to be a form of emotional enantiosemy. In her book “Слово в языке и речи” (Word in Language and Speech), she presents the following analytical example:

> Mrs. Candour: *She has a charming fresh colour.*

Lady Teazle: *Yes, when it is freshly put on.*

Mrs. Candour: *Oh, fie! I’ll swear her colour is natural; I have seen it come and go.*

Lady Teazle: *I dare swear you have, ma’am; it goes off at night, and comes again in the morning.*

Sir Benjamin: *True, ma’am, it not only comes and goes, but what’s more, egad! her maid can fetch and carry it.*

Mrs. Candour: *How I **hate** to hear you talk so! (speaking slowly, giggle) But surely, now, her sister is, or was, very handsome. (R. Sheridan)*

In this discourse, the verb “*hate*”—which typically means “*to detest*”—acquires the meaning “*to adore, to be fond of.*” The reason for this shift lies in the prosody of the verb: its tone and intonation do not correspond to its nominative (literal) meaning. The slow tempo, moderately descending pitch, unfinished intonation contour, and the accompanying paralinguistic cue—a giggle—all signal that the utterance should be interpreted positively rather than negatively.

For comparison, consider another example of the verb “*hate*” used in a typical discourse:

> “*I’ll tell you what I’m afraid of, that when you’ve gone I shall **hate** you for it.*”
(R. Bolt)

In this sentence, “*hate*” is pronounced loudly, with a high falling tone and final intonation — consistent with its negative, literal meaning. In the earlier example, however, the speaker deliberately chose a prosodically positive variant. It should be noted that the enantiosemic use of “*hate*” is characterised by paralinguistic features such as “*smile*” or “*giggle,*” which play a decisive interpretive role⁸.

Indeed, as the above examples show, the word “*hate*” in the first dialogue possesses both negative and positive evaluations. Within the dialogic discourse, the word’s evaluation becomes positive. L. V. Minayeva associates this shift solely with prosody, but in fact, evaluative amelioration occurs as a result of communicative intention and the syntactic environment appropriate to it. Not only “*hate*”, but many other linguistic units acquire positive connotations under the influence of communicative purpose, syntactic framing, and a favourable speech situation. The elements identified by Minayeva serve in spoken discourse as indicators signalling that the speaker has reversed the usual evaluation of a word. In written discourse, quotation marks often fulfil this same function.

From a pragmalinguistic standpoint, the use of a negatively evaluated word with a positive meaning, in accordance with the communicative intention and situational context, should be regarded as a re-evaluation of connotative semantics within the linguistic unit. This pragmalinguistic process occurs under the influence of the given speech situation and operates through its own semantic-pragmatic mechanisms.

The process of positive shift in negative evaluation within written discourse can be illustrated by the following examples:

⁸ Лескина С.В. Категория пейоративности в русском и английском языках в аспекте лингвокультурологического сопоставления (на материале фразеологических единиц): Автореф. дисс... д-ра. филол. наук. – Челябинск, 2010. – С. 28.

1. Under the influence of communicative intention, the usual negative evaluation of a linguistic unit—say, a word—may be rejected or attenuated by the speaker, who introduces it into a context of positive meaning. For example: “*Obbo, sen, yaramas-ey, ishni qoyillatibsan-ku!*” (“*Oh, you little rascal, you’ve done an excellent job!*”).

Here, the word *rascal*, which is typically a cacophemism carrying negative evaluation, is used positively. Within this particular discourse, it conveys praise and thus assumes a positive evaluation. This meaning and evaluation exist only in this specific context. Naturally, the tone of *rascal* in this case differs from its intonation in a genuinely negative sense. In the given discourse, the expression is uttered not with a harsh or raised tone but with a mildly affectionate, lower voice. Hence, when a speaker expresses a positive attitude toward the speech object by replacing the usual negative evaluation, an intonational modification is also observed in the speech act.

2. Socio-political and economic changes inevitably influence a national language system⁹. This mechanism may lead linguistic units that were negatively evaluated in previous periods to be perceived positively by certain groups or communities within new, non-negative contexts. Members of a speech community, instead of adhering to dictionary meanings, may use words according to their community’s shared perspective, thereby altering both their semantic and evaluative interpretations. For instance, in English, “*bad*” originally meant “*evil*” or “*inferior*,” yet in youth slang and subcultural speech, it has come to mean “*excellent, impressive, strong*.” Thus, its evaluation becomes positive. Once a subculture adopts such a reinterpretation, it may gradually spread across society, eventually entering broader linguistic usage.

According to online sources, by the late 20th and early 21st centuries, under the influence of American pop culture and the hip-hop subculture, the word “*bad*” began to be used with the meaning “*great, powerful, admirable*.” For example: “*That car is really bad!*” meaning “*That car is awesome!*”; “*He is a bad dancer*” meaning “*He is an excellent dancer*.” This phenomenon is linked to changing societal values. In youth subculture, by re-evaluating “*bad*” positively, speakers intentionally challenge conventional linguistic norms and construct their own

⁹ Лескина С.В. Категория пейоративности в русском и английском языках в аспекте лингвокультурологического сопоставления (на материале фразеологических единиц): Автореф. дисс... д-ра. филол. наук. – Челябинск, 2010. – С. 28.

sense of “prestige.” Consequently, the semantics of a word evolves under the influence of the values of a social group¹⁰.

Speakers’ tendency to express positive subjective attitudes not through conventional means but by using unusual or marked words—and the subsequent spread of such expressions to other groups—illustrates how norms of subjective evaluation can shift over time. In Uzbek, phrases such as “*yomon chiroyli o’ynadi*” (“*he played extremely well*”), *yomon zo’r ekan* (“*it was incredibly good*”), and *yomon shirin ekan* (“*it’s awfully sweet*”) exemplify cases where a negatively evaluated word (*yomon*, “*bad*”) acquires a positive connotation.

3. Pejorative expressions possess perlocutionary force, performing a controlling and influencing function on both the addressee and the audience. Because they are grounded in P. Grice’s theory of the four conversational maxims, the very category of pejorativity (negativity) confirms its pragmalinguistic status. Indeed, the properties discussed above correspond to the fundamental principles of pragmalinguistics¹¹. On this basis, when a negatively evaluated linguistic unit acquires positive connotation, this occurs through a connotative shift or a semantic-pragmatic shift. Initially, a linguistic unit transitions from a negative evaluation to a neutral one, and only subsequently—from neutral to positive evaluation. The process of such transformation can be clearly illustrated through the example of the Uzbek idiom “*aqldan ozgan*” (“*crazy*”), which in some contexts can express strong affection or admiration, as shown schematically below:

As is known, pragmalinguistics studies not only the speaker’s (addresser’s) use of language, but also the listener’s (addressee’s) comprehension, perception, and reaction. Therefore, the above example should also be analysed in terms of the perlocutionary effect of the positive shift in negative evaluation on the listener. If the speaker were not confident that the addressee would not interpret the negatively evaluated word as a direct insult—and would not perceive it as sincere—he would have chosen another linguistic unit with an originally positive

¹⁰ Why have so many ‘bad’ words gone good? // <https://www.csmonitor.com/The-Culture/In-a-Word/2022/0307/Why-have-so-many-bad-words-gone-good>

¹¹ Лескина С.В. Категория пейоративности в русском и английском языках в аспекте лингвокультурологичес-кого сопоставления (на материале фразеологических единиц): Автореф. дисс. д-ра. филол. наук. – Челябинск, 2010. – С. 10.

evaluation. Hence, the perlocutionary force should be regarded as the central mechanism scientifically substantiating the transition of linguistic units from negative connotation to positive pragmatic value.

4. In language, a negatively evaluated linguistic unit is sometimes used positively as a means of expressing affection between close friends or siblings who grew up together. For instance, the word *tentak* (meaning “foolish” or “silly”) in the utterance “**Tentak**, yana meni kuldirib yubordingiz!” (“**Silly** you, you made me laugh again!”) loses its negative evaluation. The speaker’s pragmatic intention here is not to express reproach, but rather a sincere tenderness—a subjective attitude typically reserved for a very close person. Accordingly, through the word *tentak*, a positive emotional relationship is expressed, and the addressee does not interpret the coarse word literally.

Such changes in evaluation have been noted by linguists such as N. D. Arutyunova¹², S. Ullmann¹³, and G. Leech¹⁴, who have argued that social relationships and the degree of intimacy in communication influence evaluative perception. G. Leech, in particular, provides an insightful observation: “If you must cause offence, at least do so in a way that does not openly violate the principle of politeness; let the listener reach the offensive point of your utterance indirectly, through implicature rather than explicit expression.¹⁵”

This can be supplemented by noting that the occurrence of meliorative or positive connotations in negatively evaluated words within friendly conversation demonstrates the discursive adaptability of language as a whole—and of words in particular. Such adaptability is shaped by the closeness of social relations between speaker and listener, the tone of communication, and the communicative strategy employed. These and other factors, in turn, show that the positive shift of negative evaluation, as a pragmalinguistic process, depends less on the intrinsic semantics of a word and more on its context of use and communicative intention.

5. Linguists K. O’Halloran, S. Tan, and M. Nikolas have also discussed the phenomenon of the positive shift of negative evaluation as occurring through prosody and paralinguistic means. From their analyses, one may draw the general conclusion that tone, intonation, and facial expression can alter the evaluative force of a word; in written discourse, the same function is performed by

¹²Арутюнова Н.Д. Типы языковых значений. Оценка. Событие. Факт. – М.: Наука, 1988. – С. 163.

¹³ Ullmann S. Semantics: An Introduction to the Science of Meaning. – Oxford: Basil Blackwell, 1964. – P.217-218.

¹⁴ Leech G. Principles of Pragmatics. – London: Longman, 1983 – P. 82-83

¹⁵ Leech G. Same work, p 82.

punctuation. For instance, when words such as rascal, scamp, imp, rogue, tyke, or gremlin are uttered with a smile, the listener interprets them positively rather than negatively. In this process, prosody and paralinguistic cues govern the perlocutionary effect—that is, how the utterance influences the listener's perception and emotional response¹⁶.

In all the mechanisms through which a negative evaluation may become positive, the communicative intention serves as the principal factor. For example, in the first and second types of amelioration, the speaker's aim is to enhance emotional sincerity. In the case of a connotative shift, the goal is to express one's attitude more gently, often through metaphorical or figurative means. Thus, although communicative intention is present in every instance, its modes of expression differ. From this, it follows that communicative intention may be regarded as the common pragmalinguistic foundation uniting all mechanisms of evaluative transformation.

Consequently, the positive shift of negative evaluation is not a purely linguistic phenomenon but rather a pragmalinguistic process. In the transformation of one evaluation into another, the decisive role belongs to the addresser and the speech situation. The addresser constructs a discourse consistent with his communicative intention and introduces into it words appropriate to that intention. For the positive reinterpretation of a negatively evaluated expression to occur, the discourse must also provide a syntactic environment favourable to such a reinterpretation.

There are, of course, other mechanisms that contribute to the positive shift of negative evaluation, yet all of them are ultimately governed by the addresser's communicative intention. At the same time, changes in the value system of a society may also lead to a re-evaluation of meanings, causing formerly negative words to acquire positive connotations. Therefore, in pragmalinguistic research, it is essential to consider all dimensions of the process of positive shift in negative evaluation, as it reflects both linguistic creativity and the evolving system of social values.

Used literature:

1. Емельянова Ю.И. Способы выражения оценки в научном лингвистическом дискурсе (на примере публикаций 30-х гг. XX в.) // Вестник ЧГПУ, 2010. – №2. – С. 204.
2. Арутюнова Н.Д. Типы языковых значений. Оценка. Событие. Факт. – М.: Наука, 1988. – С. 75.

¹⁶ O'Halloran K., Tan S., Nikolas M. Multimodal Pragmatics / Pragmatics of Discourse. – Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton, 2014. – P. 239-268

3. Данилова Р.Р. Категория оценки как способ выражения антропоцентризма в лингвистике // Вестник ТГГПУ, 2011. – № 23. – С. 137–139;
4. Степанова А.С. Языковые средства выражения категории оценки в публицистических текстах З.Н. Гиппиус (1920-1927 гг.). – Томск, 2016. – С. 12-13.
5. Вольф Е.М. Функциональная семантика оценки. – М.: КомКнига, 2006. – С. 5-76.
6. Ҳожиёв А. тилшунослик терминларининг изоҳли луғати. - Тошкент: “Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси” давлат илмий нашриёти, 2002. – Б. 51-52.
7. Миртожиев М. Ўзбек тили семасиологияси. - Тошкент: “Университет” нашриёти, 2010. – Б. 281-283.
8. Минаева Л.В. Слово в языке и речи. – М.: Высшая школа, 1986. – С. 127.
9. Лескина С.В. Категория пейоративности в русском и английском языках в аспекте лингвокультурологического сопоставления (на материале фразеологических единиц): Автореф. дисс... д-ра. филол. наук. – Челябинск, 2010. – С. 28.
10. Арутюнова Н.Д. Типы языковых значений. Оценка. Событие. Факт. – М.: Наука, 1988. – С. 163.
11. Ullmann S. Semantics: An Introduction to the Science of Meaning. – Oxford: Basil Blackwell, 1964. – P.217-218.
12. Leech G. Principles of Pragmatics. – London: Longman, 1983 – P. 82-83.
13. O’Halloran K., Tan S., Nikolas M. Multimodal Pragmatics / Pragmatics of Discourse. – Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton, 2014. – P. 239-268.
14. Why have so many ‘bad’ words gone good? // <https://www.csmonitor.com/The-Culture/In-a-Word/2022/0307/Why-have-so-many-bad-words-gone-good>

